

Design of 5g Based Smart City Communication Prototype

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Abstract- Recent advances in smartphones and affordable open-source hardware platforms have enabled the development of low-cost architectures for Internet-of-Things (IoT)-enabled home automation and security systems. These systems usually consist of sensing and actuating layer that is made up of sensors such as passive infrared sensors, also known as motion sensors; temperature sensors; smoke sensors, and web cameras for security surveillance. These sensors, smart electrical appliances, and other IoT devices connect to the Internet through a home gateway. This paper lays out an architecture for a cost-effective smart door sensor that will inform a user through an Android application, of door open events in a house or office environment. The proposed architecture uses an Arduino-UNO board along with the API. Several programming languages are used in the implementation and further applications of the door sensor are discussed as well as some of its shortcomings such as possible interference from other radio frequency devices.

Keywords: Internet of Things (IoT), home automation, smart security system, low-cost architecture, sensors (PIR/motion, temperature, smoke), smart devices, home gateway, smart door sensor, Arduino UNO, Android application, real-time alerts, web connectivity, API integration, wireless communication, radio frequency interference.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of things (IoT) is the network of physical devices, vehicles, home appliances and other items embedded with electronics, software, sensors, actuators, and network connectivity which enable these objects to connect and exchange data. Each thing is uniquely identifiable through its embedded computing system but is able to inter-operate within the existing Internet infrastructure. Experts estimate that the IoT will consist of about 30 billion objects by 2020. It is also estimated that the global market value of IoT will reach \$7.1 trillion by 2020. The IoT allows objects to be sensed or controlled remotely across existing network infrastructure, creating opportunities for more direct integration of the physical world into computer-based systems, and resulting in improved efficiency, accuracy and economic benefit in addition to reduced human intervention. When IoT is augmented with sensors and actuators, the technology becomes an instance of the more general class of cyber-physical systems, which also encompasses technologies such as smart grids, virtual power plants, smart homes, intelligent transportation and smart cities. "Things", in the IoT sense, can refer to a wide variety of devices such as heart monitoring implants, biochip transponders on farm animals, cameras streaming live feeds of wild animals in coastal waters, automobiles with built-in sensors, DNA analysis devices for environmental/food/pathogen monitoring, or field operation devices that assist fire fighters in search and rescue operations.

Legal scholars suggest regarding "things" as an "inextricable mixture of hardware, software, data and service".

II. WORKING PRINCIPAL

In order to address the mentioned issues of flexibility and functionality in the literature survey, we designed and implemented a flexible and low cost home controlling system using Serial Wi-Fi Module. The system consists of a Web – server based on Arduino Wi-Fi, hardware interface modules and the Android compatible Smart phone app. The architecture presented in this work can be customized in different ways in order to accommodate different application scenarios with minimum recoding and design i.e. each time a new device is added to the Web-server, a new thread dedicated to the device is has to be created in the Smart phone app. This system allows authorized home owners to remotely control and monitor connected devices at home using any wired portion. The smart phone app provides a graphical user interface (GUI) for accessing and controlling the devices at home through server real IP

III. HARDWARE DESCRIPTION

Water Level Sensor

If you've ever had a water heater explode or attempted to build submersible electronics, you know how important it is to detect the presence of water. That is exactly what this Water Level

Sensor allows you to do! It can measure the water level, monitor a sump pit, detect rainfall, and detect leaks. Let's look into this sensor in more detail.

Hardware Overview

The sensor has ten exposed copper traces, five of which are power traces and the remaining five are sense traces. These traces are interlaced so that there is one sense trace between every two power traces.

Normally, power and sense traces are not connected, but when immersed in water, they are bridged.

There is a Power LED on the board, which will light up when the board is powered.

How Does a Water Level Sensor Work

The operation of the water level sensor is fairly simple. The power and sense traces form a variable resistor (much like a potentiometer) whose resistance varies based on how much they are exposed to water.

This resistance varies inversely with the depth of immersion of the sensor in water:

- The more water the sensor is immersed in, the better the conductivity and the lower the resistance.
- The less water the sensor is immersed in, the poorer the conductivity and the higher the resistance.

The sensor generates an output voltage proportional to the resistance; by measuring this voltage, the water level can be determined.

IV. WATER LEVEL SENSOR PINOUT

The water level sensor is extremely simple to use and only requires three pins to connect.

S (SIGNAL) - Is an analog output pin that will be connected to one of your Arduino analog inputs.

+ (VCC)- Pin provides power to the sensor. It is recommended that the sensor be powered from 3.3V to 5V. Please keep in mind that the analog output will vary depending on the voltage supplied to the sensor.

(GND) is the ground pin.

Wiring a Water Level Sensor to an Arduino

Let's hook up the water level sensor to the Arduino.

To begin, connect the + (VCC) pin on the module to 5V on the Arduino and the - (GND) pin to ground.

One well-known issue with these sensors is that they have a shorter lifespan because they are constantly exposed to moisture. Moreover, constantly applying power to the sensor while immersed in water significantly accelerates the rate of corrosion.

To avoid this, it is recommended that the sensor be turned on only when taking readings.

One easy way to do this is to connect the sensor's power pin to a digital pin on an Arduino and set it to HIGH or LOW as needed. So, we'll connect the + (VCC) pin to the Arduino's digital pin #7.

Finally, connect the S (Signal) pin to the Arduino's A0 ADC pin.

V. TEMPERATURE SENSOR (DHT11)

The DHT11 humidity and temperature sensor makes it really easy to add humidity and temperature data to your DIY electronics projects. It's perfect for remote weather stations, home environmental control systems, and farm or garden monitoring systems.

I'll first go into a little background about humidity, then I'll explain how the DHT11 measures humidity. After that, I'll show you how to connect the DHT11 to an Arduino and give you some example code so you can use the DHT11 in your own projects.

VI. WHAT IS RELATIVE TEMPERATURE/HUMIDITY

The DHT11 measures relative humidity. Relative humidity is the amount of water vapor in air vs. the saturation point of water vapor in air. At the saturation point, water vapor starts to condense and accumulate on surfaces forming dew.

The saturation point changes with air temperature. Cold air can hold less water vapor before it becomes saturated, and hot air can hold more water vapor before it becomes saturated. Relative humidity is expressed as a percentage. At 100% RH, condensation occurs, and at 0% RH, the air is completely dry.

How The Dht11 Measures Humidity And Temperature

The DHT11 detects water vapor by measuring the electrical resistance between two electrodes. The humidity sensing component is a moisture holding substrate with electrodes applied to the surface. When water vapor is absorbed by the substrate, ions are released by the substrate which increases the conductivity between the electrodes. The change in resistance between the two electrodes is proportional to the relative humidity. Higher relative humidity decreases the resistance between the electrodes, while lower relative humidity increases the resistance between the electrodes.

The DHT11 measures temperature with a surface mounted NTC temperature sensor (thermistor) built into the unit. To learn more about how thermistors work and how to use them on the Arduino, check out our Arduino Thermistor Temperature Sensor Tutorial.

With the plastic housing removed, you can see the electrodes applied to the substrate

An IC mounted on the back of the unit converts the resistance measurement to relative humidity. It also stores the calibration coefficients, and controls the data signal transmission between the DHT11 and the Arduino:

The DHT11 uses just one signal wire to transmit data to the Arduino. Power comes from separate 5V and ground wires. A 10K Ohm pull-up resistor is needed between the signal line and 5V line to make sure the signal level stays high by default (see the datasheet for more info).

There are two different versions of the DHT11 you might come across. One type has four pins, and the other type has three pins and is mounted to a small PCB. The PCB mounted version is nice because it includes a surface mounted 10K Ohm pull up resistor for the signal line. Here are the pin outs for both versions:

for the Arduino platform; for an extensive list of current, past or outdated boards see the Arduino index of boards.

This is the Arduino Uno R3. In addition to all the features of the previous board, the Uno now uses an ATmega16U2 instead of the 8U2 found on the Uno (or the FTDI found on previous generations). This allows for faster transfer rates and more memory. No drivers needed for Linux or Mac (inf file for Windows is needed and included in the Arduino IDE), and the ability to have the Uno show up as a keyboard, mouse, joystick, etc.

The Uno R3 also adds SDA and SCL pins next to the AREF. In addition, there are two new pins placed near the RESET pin. One is the IOREF that allow the shields to adapt to the voltage provided from the board. The other is a not connected and is reserved for future purposes. The Uno R3 works with all existing shields but can adapt to new shields which use these additional pins.

The Arduino Uno is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328. Arduino is an open-source, prototyping platform and its simplicity makes it ideal for hobbyists to use as well as professionals. The Arduino Uno has 14 digital input/output pins (of which 6 can be used as PWM outputs), 6 analog inputs, a 16 MHz crystal oscillator, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It contains everything needed to support the microcontroller; simply connect it to a computer with a USB cable or power it with a AC-to-DC adapter or battery to get started.

VII. ARDUINO UNO CONTROLLER

The Arduino Uno is a microcontroller board based on the ATmega328. It has 14 digital input/output pins (of which six can be used as PWM outputs), six analog inputs, a 16 MHz crystal oscillator, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It contains everything needed to support the microcontroller; simply connect it to a computer with a USB cable or power it with an AC-to-DC adapter or battery to get started. The Arduino Uno differs from all preceding boards because it does not use the FTDI USB-to-serial driver chip. Instead, it features the ATmega8U2 programmed as a USB-to-serial converter. Revision 2 of the Arduino Uno board has a resistor pulling the 8U2 HWB line to ground, making it easier to put into DFU mode.

"Uno" means one in Italian and was chosen to mark the release of Arduino Software (IDE) 1.0. The Uno board and version 1.0 of Arduino Software (IDE) were the reference versions of Arduino, now evolved to newer releases. The Uno board is the first in a series of USB Arduino boards, and the reference model

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"Uno" means one in Italian and is named to mark the upcoming release of Arduino 1.0. The Arduino Uno and version 1.0 will be the reference versions of Arduino, moving forward. The Uno is the latest in a series of USB Arduino boards, and the reference model for the Arduino platform.

VIII. PROGRAMMING

The Arduino Uno can be programmed with the (Arduino Software (IDE)). Select "Arduino/Genuino Uno from the Tools > Board menu (according to the microcontroller on your board). For details, see the reference and tutorials. The ATmega328 on the Arduino Uno comes pre-programmed with a boot loader that allows you to upload new code to it without the use of an external hardware programmer. It communicates using the original STK500 protocol (reference, C header files). You can also bypass the boot loader and program the microcontroller through the ICSP (In-Circuit Serial Programming) header using Arduino ISP or similar; see these instructions for details.

The ATmega16U2 (or 8U2 in the rev1 and rev2 boards) firmware source code is available in the Arduino repository. The ATmega16U2/8U2 is loaded with a DFU boot loader, which can be activated by: On Rev1 boards: connecting the solder jumper on the back of the board (near the map of Italy) and then rising the 8U2. On Rev2 or later boards: there is a resistor that pulling the 8U2/16U2 HWB line to ground, making it easier to put into DFU mode. You can then use Atmel's FLIP software (Windows) or the DFU programmer (Mac OS X and Linux) to load a new firmware. Or you can use the ISP header with an external programmer (overwriting the DFU boot loader)

Power

AC-DC adapter (wall-wart) or battery. The adapter can be connected by plugging a 2.1mm center-positive plug into the board's power jack. Leads from a battery can be inserted in the GND and Vin pin headers of the POWER connector. The board can operate on an external supply from 6 to 20 volts. If supplied with less than 7V, however, the 5V pin may supply less than five volts and the board may become unstable. If using more than 12V, the voltage regulator may overheat and damage the board. The recommended range is 7 to 12 volts.

Vin. The input voltage to the Arduino/Genuino board when it's using an external power source (as opposed to 5 volts from the USB connection or other regulated power source). You can

supply voltage through this pin, or, if supplying voltage via the power jack, access it through this pin. 5V. This pin outputs a regulated 5V from the regulator on the board. The board can be supplied with power either from the DC power jack (7 - 12V), the USB connector (5V), or the VIN pin of the board (7-12V). Supplying voltage via the 5V or 3.3V pins bypasses the regulator, and can damage your board. We don't advise it. 3V3. A 3.3 volt supply generated by the on-board regulator. Maximum current draw is 50 mA. GND. Ground pins. IOREF. This pin on the Arduino/Genuino board provides the voltage reference with which the microcontroller operates. A properly configured shield can read the IOREF pin voltage and select the appropriate power source or enable voltage translators on the outputs to work with the 5V or 3.3V.

Input and Output

Serial: 0 (RX) and 1 (TX). Used to receive (RX) and transmit (TX) TTL serial data. These pins are connected to the corresponding pins of the ATmega8U2 USB-to-TTL Serial chip.

External Interrupts: 2 and 3. These pins can be configured to trigger an interrupt on a low value, a rising or falling edge, or a change in value. See the attach Interrupt() function for details.

PWM: 3, 5, 6, 9, 10, and 11. Provide 8-bit PWM output with the analogWrite() function. SPI: 10 (SS), 11 (MOSI), 12 (MISO), 13 (SCK). These pins support SPI communication using the SPI library.

LED: 13. There is a built-in LED driven by digital pin 13. When the pin is HIGH value, the LED is on, when the pin is LOW, it's off.

TWI: A4 or SDA pin and A5 or SCL pin. Support TWI communication using the Wire library.

The Uno has 6 analog inputs, labelled A0 through A5, each of which provide 10 bits of resolution (i.e. 1024 different values). By default they measure from ground to 5 volts, though is it possible to change the upper end of their range using the AREF pin and the analog Reference() function. There are a couple of other pins on the board:

AREF. Reference voltage for the analog inputs. Used with analog Reference().

Reset. Bring this line LOW to reset the microcontroller. Typically used to add a reset button to shields which block the one on the board.

IX. COMMUNICATION

Arduino/Genuino Uno has a number of facilities for communicating with a computer, another Arduino/Genuino board, or other microcontrollers. The ATmega328 provides UART TTL (5V) serial communication, which is available on digital pins 0 (RX) and 1 (TX). An ATmega16U2 on the board channels this serial communication over USB and appears as a virtual com port to software on the computer. The 16U2 firmware uses the standard USB COM drivers, and no external driver is needed. However, on Windows, a .inf file is required. The Arduino Software (IDE) includes a serial monitor which allows simple textual data to be sent to and from the board. The RX and TX LEDs on the board will flash when data is being transmitted via the USB-to-serial chip and USB connection to the computer (but not for serial communication on pins 0 and 1).

The ATmega328 also supports I2C (TWI) and SPI communication. The Arduino Software (IDE) includes a Wire library to simplify use of the I2C bus; see the documentation for details. For SPI communication, use the SPI library

X. AUTOMATIC (SOFTWARE) RESET

Rather than requiring a physical press of the reset button before an upload, the Arduino/Genuino Uno board is designed in a way that allows it to be reset by software running on a connected computer. One of the hardware flow control lines (DTR) of the ATmega8U2/16U2 is connected to the reset line of the ATmega328 via a 100 nano farad capacitor. When this line is asserted (taken low), the reset line drops long enough to reset the chip. The Arduino Software (IDE) uses this capability to allow you to upload code by simply pressing the upload button in the interface toolbar. This means that the boot loader can have a shorter timeout, as the lowering of DTR can be well-coordinated with the start of the upload. This setup has other implications. When the Uno is connected to either a computer running Mac OS X or Linux, it resets each time a connection is made to it from software (via USB). For the following half-second or so, the boot loader is running on the Uno. While it is programmed to ignore malformed data (i.e. anything besides an upload of new code), it will intercept the first few bytes of data sent to the board after a connection is opened. If a sketch running on the board receives one-time configuration or other data when it first starts, make sure that the software with which it communicates waits a second after opening the connection and before sending this data. The Uno board contains a trace that can be cut to disable the auto-reset. The pads on either side of the trace can be soldered together to re-enable it. It's labelled

"RESET-EN". You may also be able to disable the auto-reset by connecting a 110 ohm resistor from 5V to the reset line; see this forum thread for details.

XI. IOT SOFTWARE

IoT software addresses its key areas of networking and action through platforms, embedded systems, partner systems, and middleware. These individual and master applications are responsible for data collection, device integration, real-time analytics, and application and process extension within the IoT network. They exploit integration with critical business systems (e.g., ordering systems, robotics, scheduling, and more) in the execution of related tasks.

Data Collection

This software manages sensing, measurements, light data filtering, light data security, and aggregation of data. It uses certain protocols to aid sensors in connecting with real-time, machine-to-machine networks. Then it collects data from multiple devices and distributes it in accordance with settings. It also works in reverse by distributing data over devices. The system eventually transmits all collected data to a central server.

Device Integration

Software supporting integration binds (dependent relationships) all system devices to create the body of the IoT system. It ensures the necessary cooperation and stable networking between devices. These applications are the defining software technology of the IoT network because without them, it is not an IoT system. They manage the various applications, protocols, and limitations of each device to allow communication.

Real-Time Analytics

These applications take data or input from various devices and convert it into viable actions or clear patterns for human analysis. They analyze information based on various settings and designs in order to perform automation-related tasks or provide the data required by industry.

Application and Process Extension

These applications extend the reach of existing systems and software to allow a wider, more effective system. They integrate predefined devices for specific purposes such as allowing certain mobile devices or engineering instruments access. It supports improved productivity and more accurate data collection.

XII. WATER PUMP

The water pump can be defined as a pump which uses the principles like mechanical as well as hydraulic throughout a piping system and to make sufficient force for its future use. They have been approximately in one structure otherwise another because of early civilization. At present these pumps are utilized within a wide range of housing, farming, municipal, and manufacturing applications.

Block Diagram Control Section

Water Pump Working Principle

The working principle of a water pump mainly depends upon the positive displacement principle as well as kinetic energy to push the water. These pumps use AC power otherwise DC power for energizing the motor of the water pump whereas others can be energized other kinds of drivers like gasoline engines otherwise diesel.

The water pump is a portable device and can be applied in several household applications. These pumps are used for pumping the huge amount of water from one place to another. The main purpose of a water pump is versatile. A quality pump which can be selected carefully may be perfect for draining water from a low flooded region, refilling the swimming pool, and bathtub, circulating pesticides otherwise fertilizers.

The collection of water pumps are very large, therefore, while selecting a strong and consistent one, one should think about the requirement.

Types of Water Pumps

Water pumps are classified into two types namely positive displacement and centrifugal. These pumps are mainly designed for supplying water from one location to another constantly.

Centrifugal Water Pump

Centrifugal pumps are designed with a rotating impeller which can be used for supplying the water into the pump and force the discharge flow. These pumps come in several types which includes trash, submersible, and standard models. By using these pumps, all types of liquids can be pumped with low-viscosity. And also these pumps work fine with thin fluids & gives high flow rates.

Considerations

These pumps are applicable in several applications like building as well as the water system. These pumps are used to provide water supplies for buildings and well-matched with pneumatic systems where the no-suction lift is necessary. The main purpose of these water pumps is to pump water from wells in homes & to increase water pressure in intake lines. Centrifugal pumps offer a nonstop pressure supply for fire guard systems, and they can supply like sump pumps in horizontal otherwise vertical configurations.

Centrifugal pumps are horizontal to numerous general problems. These may require liquid circulation to stop overheating which is caused by low supplies. These types of pumps must be prepared to work properly. As a head of the positive suction system is very less while selecting the pump, it can consequence to cavitations, a situation wherever air bubbles form close to the impeller, then leads to shock signals within the water pump. At last, wear of the impeller of the pump can be degenerated by delayed solids within the fluid.

Positive Displacement Water Pump

Positive displacement pumps supply a set amount of flow throughout the mechanical contraction and development of a stretchy diaphragm. These pumps are applicable in several industries that control high-viscosity fluids wherever responsive solids may be there. These are suggested for the applications wherever a combination of high pressure and low flow is required.

How To Choose The Pump

There are some factors need to be considered while selecting the pump that includes the following.

Material: The pump material should be weather-resistant for exposed uses.

POWER: The power of the pump mainly includes horsepower & the flow rate.

Type of Fuel and Motor:

The motor and fuel of the pump should be electric motor, gas, hydraulic, diesel, otherwise manual.

Head: The total head expulsion, otherwise utmost pump power, appropriate for the proposed application

Applications of Water Pumps

Water pumps are used for dewatering reasons decreasing the downtime from huge rain events. The common applications of these pumps include buildings, wells, boost application, circulation of hot water, sump pits, protection of fire systems, etc.

Thus, this is all about water pumps which are frequently used in construction fields for removing surplus water as well as dewatering. Because of heavy rains, the flow of water can increase & water pumps let you supply the water rapidly to reduce downtime. These pumps are appropriate for applications like electric, hydraulic, gas-powered, and otherwise manual. These pumps are vast addition to our life because they make possible a huge variety of industrial, agricultural and household tasks. But, the variety of water pumps in the marketplace is so adaptable and plentiful that selecting the correct pump appropriate for your requirements is challenging.

L293d Motor Driver Ic Introduction

The L293 and L293D are quadruple high-current half-H drivers. The L293 is designed to provide bidirectional drive currents of up to 1A at voltages from 4.5 V to 36 V. The L293D is designed to provide bidirectional drive currents of up to 600-

mA at voltages from 4.5 V to 36 V. Both devices are designed to drive inductive loads such as relays, solenoids, dc and bipolar stepping motors, as well as other high-current/high-voltage loads in positive supply applications.

All inputs are TTL compatible. Each output is a complete totem-pole drive circuit with a Darlington transistor sink and a pseudo Darlington source. Drivers are enabled in pairs, with drivers 1 and 2 enabled by 1, 2 EN and drivers 3 and 4 enabled by 3, 4 EN. When an enable input is high, the associated drivers are enabled, and their outputs are active and in phase with their inputs. When the enable input is low, those drivers are disabled, and their outputs are off and in the high-impedance state. With the proper data inputs, each pair of drivers forms a full-H (or bridge) reversible drive suitable for solenoid or motor applications.

Figure No. 5.1 L293D Motor Driver IC

Features of L293D Motor Driver IC

- Wide Supply-Voltage Range 4.5 V to 36 V.
- Separate Input-Logic supply.
- Internal ESD protection.
- Thermal Shutdown.
- High-Noise-Immunity Inputs.
- Functionally similar to L293
- Output current 600-mA.

XIII. CONCLUSION

In this project, we incorporated three different systems such as garbage monitoring, gas leakage detection and accident detection system by means of internet. By using this system people do not have to check all the system manually but they will get a notification.

The Internet of Things facilitates a numerous benefits to the society and from our project we can provide and prove the

strength of IOT using the Thing Speak API that is capable to contribute the services for the purpose of building vast number of IOT applications and help to implement them on the public platform. This Design Provides moderate and less expensive way of sensing and monitoring system. The future of MATLAB in Thing Speak provides an analysis of sensed data at a critical level that is to manage the surrounding environment where the parameters are important to measure. At an final note we conclude that Microcontrollers will get minimize and vanish into the environment, and IOT Leads to become everywhere and universal in every prospect.

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